

Densities and apparent molar volumes of oxalic acid in water and in aqueous solutions of sucrose at 293.15, 303.15, 313.15 and 323.15 K

Radha Rani Gupta and Mukhtar Singh*

Department of Chemistry, Agra College, Agra-282 002, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : mukhtarsingh2003@rediffmail.com

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Abstract : Apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ) of oxalic acid in water and in aqueous sucrose solutions with concentrations $\approx(0.5-2.0)$ mol kg⁻¹ have been determined as a function of molality by measuring the densities at 293.15, 303.15, 313.15 and 323.15 K. From these data the limiting apparent molar volume (V_ϕ^0), which is equal to the partial molar volume at infinite dilution (V_ϕ^0), has been obtained at different temperatures. The partial molar volumes have been used to calculate the partial molar volumes of transfer (ΔV_ϕ^0) of oxalic acid from water to aqueous sucrose solutions. The values of limiting apparent molar expansibilities, (ϕ_E^0) and that of $(\partial^2 V_\phi^0/\partial T^2)_p$ have also been determined from temperature-dependence of V_ϕ^0 at various concentrations of the sucrose solutions. The results have been discussed in terms of various interactions operating in oxalic acid, water and sucrose systems.

Keywords : Density, molar volume, oxalic acid, sucrose.

A survey of literature¹⁻²⁰ reveals that although many studies on thermodynamic properties of different types of solutes have been carried out in single solvent or in mixed solvent systems, little attention has been paid to the behaviour of carboxylic acids in different solvent systems. Recently, Parmar *et al.*²¹ have reported studies on the determination of partial molar volumes of citric and tartaric acids in water and binary aqueous mixtures of ethanol of varying compositions at different temperatures and acid concentrations from the density data. It has been concluded that the partial molar volumes of these acids vary with temperature as a power series of temperature. Structure making/breaking capacities of the acids have been inferred from the sign of $(\partial^2 V_\phi^0/\partial T^2)_p$. Both the acids behave as structure breakers in water and (ethanol + water) mixed solvents. In another publication Parmar and coworkers²² have also carried out a study on partial molar volumes of ascorbic, citric and tartaric acids in binary aqueous solutions of urea at different concentrations and temperatures. The data have been analysed using Masson's equation²³ and solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions have been discussed in the light of the constants V_ϕ^0 and S_v of Masson's equation. From the temperature dependence of V_ϕ^0 , the values of $(\partial^2 V_\phi^0/\partial T^2)_p$ have been obtained and structure making/breaking capacities of the organic acids have been inferred from the sign of $(\partial^2 V_\phi^0/\partial T^2)_p$. The

results of the study reveal that all the three acids behave as structure breakers in binary aqueous solutions of urea.

From the above described survey of literature it is seen that comprehensive studies relating to the densities and apparent molar volumes of oxalic acid in water and in aqueous solutions of sucrose (as solvent) vis-a-vis solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions are still lacking. Hence the title study has been undertaken.

Results and discussion

The apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ) of oxalic acid in water and in aqueous solutions of sucrose have been determined employing the following equation,

$$V_\phi = \frac{1000(\rho_0 - \rho)}{m\rho\rho_0} + \frac{M}{\rho} \quad (1)$$

where M is molecular weight of solute (oxalic acid), m is the molality of the solution, ρ and ρ_0 denote the densities of solution and solvent, respectively.

The measured densities (ρ_0) of water and aqueous solutions of sucrose (used as solvents) at 293.15, 303.15, 313.15 and 323.15 K are presented in Table 1. The densities (ρ) and apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ) of solutions of oxalic acid in water and in aqueous solutions of sucrose have been determined as a function of molality at different

*Address for correspondence : H.I.G. 142, Phase A, Shastri Puram, Sikandra, Agra-282 007, Uttar Pradesh, India.

Table 1. Densities (ρ_0) of water and aqueous solutions of sucrose (as solvents) at different temperatures

Molality (m) of sucrose solutions (mol kg ⁻¹)	ρ_0 (g cm ⁻³)			
	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K	323.15 K
0.0 (water)	0.9982	0.9957	0.9922	0.9881
0.5614	1.0618	1.0585	1.0550	1.0510
1.2838	1.1215	1.1197	1.1155	1.1106
2.2340	1.1900	1.1847	1.1802	1.1748
3.5457	1.2633	1.2583	1.2534	1.2482

temperatures and the representative data at 293.15 K are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Densities (ρ) and apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ) of solutions of oxalic acid as a function of molality at different temperatures in water and in aqueous solutions of sucrose

$m_s = 0.0$ mol kg ⁻¹			$m_s = 0.5614$ mol kg ⁻¹			$m_s = 1.2838$ mol kg ⁻¹			$m_s = 2.2340$ mol kg ⁻¹			$m_s = 3.5457$ mol kg ⁻¹		
m mol kg ⁻¹	ρ g cm ⁻³	V_ϕ cm ³ mol ⁻¹	m mol kg ⁻¹	ρ g cm ⁻³	V_ϕ cm ³ mol ⁻¹	m mol kg ⁻¹	ρ g cm ⁻³	V_ϕ cm ³ mol ⁻¹	m mol kg ⁻¹	ρ g cm ⁻³	V_ϕ cm ³ mol ⁻¹	m mol kg ⁻¹	ρ g cm ⁻³	V_ϕ cm ³ mol ⁻¹
Temp. 293.15 K														
0.2043	1.0044	95.60	0.1910	1.0722	69.85	0.1804	1.1341	56.20	0.1696	1.2047	44.10	0.1602	1.2739	57.60
0.3091	1.0085	92.00	0.2888	1.0768	71.70	0.2721	1.1403	56.34	0.2555	1.2119	44.60	0.2418	1.2785	59.52
0.4154	1.0134	88.40	0.3880	1.0812	72.93	0.3650	1.1464	56.75	0.3424	1.2185	46.00	0.3246	1.2826	61.46
0.5231	1.0188	85.00	0.4893	1.0849	75.11	0.4591	1.1520	57.93	0.4302	1.2252	46.85	0.4088	1.2860	63.80
0.6309	1.0266	78.89	0.5918	1.0896	75.11	0.5544	1.1579	58.25	0.5189	1.2319	47.20	0.4938	1.2906	63.68
0.7410	1.0329	76.62	0.6956	1.0946	74.60	0.6499	1.1654	56.47	0.6085	1.2386	47.60	0.5800	1.2952	63.72
0.8540	1.0376	77.00	0.8008	1.0999	73.87	0.7495	1.1683	60.20	0.6995	1.2446	48.60	0.6677	1.2990	64.46
0.9659	1.0452	74.00	0.9093	1.1033	75.33	0.8475	1.1754	59.00	0.7909	1.2514	48.60	0.7579	1.3010	66.65
1.0762	1.0552	69.20	1.0192	1.1072	75.97	0.9485	1.1803	59.90	0.8848	1.2562	50.30	0.8463	1.3077	64.60

m_s = molality of sucrose solution.

Plots of V_ϕ versus m are linear at 293.15, 303.15, 313.15 and 323.15 K. The V_ϕ - m data are therefore fitted by the following equation,

$$V_\phi = V_\phi^0 + S_v m \quad (2)$$

where V_ϕ^0 is the limiting apparent molar volume (which is equal to the partial molar volume at infinite dilution, V_2^0) and S_v is the experimental slope. V_ϕ^0 is a measure of solute-solvent interactions while S_v is a measure of solute-solute interactions.

The values of V_ϕ^0 and S_v have been evaluated by computerized least-square fitting to eq. (2) and are listed in Table 3 along with standard deviation (σ) of the fit. It is seen that the values of V_ϕ^0 for oxalic acid in purely aqueous solutions are positive at different temperatures. The positive large values of V_ϕ^0 for oxalic acid in water

indicate the presence of strong solute-solvent interactions in purely aqueous solutions. However, a sharp decrease in the value of V_ϕ^0 in the presence of aqueous solutions of sucrose occurs which suggests that strength of solute-solvent interaction is reduced with increasing concentration of sucrose. Table 3 shows that with the rise of temperature the values of V_ϕ^0 of oxalic acid become larger both in purely aqueous solutions as well as in aqueous solutions of sucrose. Solute-solvent interactions are rendered more stronger with the rise of temperature, which may be attributed to increased solvation of oxalic acid molecules at higher temperatures.

Table 3 shows that the values of S_v in purely aqueous solutions of oxalic acid are largely negative which indicate

the presence of weak solute-solute interactions. However, in the presence of sucrose, the values of S_v become positive which suggest that solute-solute interactions in the solutions of oxalic acid in the presence of sucrose become stronger. We thus anticipate that solvent-solvent interaction through hydrogen bonding between water and sucrose molecules seems to be sufficiently strong to prevent (the expected) increase in solute-solvent interaction as the amount of sucrose in the solution increases. This explains the lower values of V_ϕ^0 for oxalic acid in aqueous sucrose solutions (as solvent) as compared to those in water.

Partial molar volumes of transfer (ΔV_ϕ^0) of oxalic acid from water to aqueous solutions of sucrose (as solvent) at infinite dilution are calculated from the following equation,

$$\Delta V_\phi^0 = V_\phi^0 \text{ (in aq. sucrose solution)} - V_\phi^0 \text{ (in water)} \quad (3)$$

Table 3. Limiting apparent molar volume (V_{ϕ}^0) and experimental slope (S_v) of solutions of oxalic acid in water and in aqueous solutions of sucrose at different temperatures

Sucrose (mol kg ⁻¹)	V_{ϕ}^0 (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)				S_v (cm ³ dm ^{3/2} mol ^{-3/2})				σ^a			
	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K	323.15 K	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K	323.15 K	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K	323.15 K
0.0 (water)	100.33	102.91	105.39	106.05	-29.06	-30.59	-28.40	-27.32	0.0103	0.0024	0.0010	0.0115
0.5614	70.32	74.30	77.19	78.19	5.87	4.27	3.94	3.39	0.0002	0.0008	0.0017	0.0013
*1.2838	55.15	62.39	66.02	68.47	4.91	4.15	3.81	1.56	0.0007	0.0004	0.0011	0.0009
2.2340	42.93	43.44	48.78	48.94	7.97	6.68	5.74	3.64	0.0005	0.0006	0.0014	0.0009
3.5457	57.52	58.04	58.79	61.85	10.68	9.13	7.38	5.48	0.0002	0.0015	0.0000	0.0009

^aStandard deviation of the fit of eq. (2).

The results are presented in Fig. 1. It is seen that the values of ΔV_{ϕ}^0 are negative which may be attributed to the increase in electrostriction in the presence of aqueous solutions of sucrose. The electrostriction effect, which brings about shrinkage in the volume of solvent, is increased in the presence of aqueous solutions of sucrose as compared to in pure water. On plotting the value of ΔV_{ϕ}^0 against molality (m) of aqueous solutions of sucrose (Fig. 1), it is seen that at each temperature the plot is characterised by a minimal value of ΔV_{ϕ}^0 at $m \approx 2.25$ mol kg⁻¹. From this it follows that shrinkage in the volume of

Fig. 1. Variation of volume of transfer (ΔV_{ϕ}^0) of oxalic acid against m (mol kg⁻¹) of aqueous solutions of sucrose at (O) 293.15, (□) 303.15, (Δ) 313.15 and (◇) 323.15 K.

sucrose solutions increases with increasing amount of sucrose and that at $m \approx 2.25$ mol kg⁻¹ this shrinkage is maximum. Thereafter the shrinkage in volume becomes smaller at higher content of sucrose in aqueous solutions. The negative values of ΔV_{ϕ}^0 may be attributed^{24,25} to group interactions between ions of oxalic acid and hydrophobic parts of sucrose molecule.

The variation of V_{ϕ}^0 with the temperature can be expressed²⁶ as,

$$V_{\phi}^0 = a_0 + a_1T + a_2T^2 \quad (4)$$

The values of coefficients a_i have been calculated by least squares fitting of the V_{ϕ}^0 -temperature (T) data into eq. (4) and are listed in Table 4.

Table 4. Values of coefficients a_i for solutions of oxalic acid in water and in aqueous solutions of sucrose (temperature dependence of V_{ϕ}^0)

Sucrose m (mol kg ⁻¹)	Oxalic acid		
	a_0	a_1	a_2
0.0 (water)	-412.0	3.155	-0.0048
0.5614	-711.5	4.846	-0.0074
1.2838	-1208.5	7.827	-0.0120
2.2340	-110.8	0.785	-0.0009
3.5457	619.8	-3.782	0.0064

The limiting apparent molar expansibilities, ϕ_E^0 have been calculated from the following relation,

$$\phi_E^0 = (\partial V_{\phi}^0 / \partial T)_P = a_1 + 2a_2T \quad (5)$$

ϕ_E^0 decreases with the rise of temperature in purely aqueous solutions of oxalic acid and also in aqueous sucrose solutions with molalities ≈ 0.56 – 2.25 mol kg⁻¹. This decrease in the value of ϕ_E^0 with the rise in temperature indicates that behaviour of oxalic acid is just like common electrolytes^{27,28}. This conclusion is in agreement with that reported by Parmar *et al.*^{21,22} in respect of citric, tartaric and ascorbic acids. However, at higher concentration ($m \approx 3.5$ mol kg⁻¹) of sucrose solutions ϕ_E^0 tends to increase with rise of temperature. This may be ascribed to the presence of caging effect²⁸ in relatively concentrated solutions of sucrose (as solvent).

Hepler²⁹ has proposed a method by which qualitative information on hydration of solutes can be obtained from thermal expansion of aqueous solution by the following relation,

$$(\partial C_P^0/\partial P)_T = -T(\partial^2 V_\phi^0/\partial T^2)_P \quad (6)$$

According to this, the left hand side of the above equation should be positive for all structure-breaking solutes and therefore, structure breaking solutes possess negative value of $(\partial^2 V_\phi^0/\partial T^2)_P$. On the other hand, positive value of $(\partial^2 V_\phi^0/\partial T^2)_P$ should be associated with structure making solutes. In the present study the values of $(\partial^2 V_\phi^0/\partial T^2)_P$ have been obtained from eq. (5) and it is found that the values of $(\partial^2 V_\phi^0/\partial T^2)_P$ for oxalic acid are negative in purely aqueous solutions and also in aqueous sucrose solutions with molalities ≈ 0.56 – 2.25 mol kg^{-1} . However, at higher molality, $m \approx 3.5 \text{ mol kg}^{-1}$, the value of $(\partial^2 V_\phi^0/\partial T^2)_P$ becomes positive. The negative values of $(\partial^2 V_\phi^0/\partial T^2)_P$ suggest that oxalic acid behaves as a structure-breaker in pure water and also in aqueous sucrose solutions with molalities ≈ 0.56 – 2.25 mol kg^{-1} . However, at higher content of sucrose ($m \approx 3.5 \text{ mol kg}^{-1}$) in aqueous solutions, oxalic acid tends to become structure maker.

Experimental

Oxalic acid (mol. wt. 126) was a B.D.H. product of analytical reagent grade. Sucrose (mol. wt. 342) of the highest purity (99.9%) was obtained from Sigma Chemical Company (USA). These were dried over P_2O_5 in a vacuum desiccator. Standard stock solutions of oxalic acid and sucrose were prepared using water having specific conductance $\approx 10^{-6} \Omega \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which was degassed before use. All the solutions were prepared afresh on a molarity scale. Weighing was done on a Mettler balance having an accuracy of $\pm 1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ g}$.

The densities of solutions were measured at 293.15, 303.15, 313.15 and 323.15 K by using digital vibrating tube densimeter (Model 60/602 Anton Parr, Austria). The temperature of the water flowing around the densimeter cell was controlled within $\pm 0.01 \text{ K}$ using an efficient temperature bath. The uncertainties of the density measurements were estimated to be $\pm 1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ g cm}^{-3}$.

The molalities (m) of the solutions were calculated from the molarities (C) using the following equation³⁰,

$$m = \frac{1}{(\rho/C) - (M/1000)} \quad (7)$$

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